

control, blood pressure management, and lifestyle modification to reduce recurrence risk. From a pathophysiological perspective, small cortical infarcts in the hand-knob region are usually supplied by distal branches of the middle cerebral artery. Infarction can result from a variety of mechanisms, including small-vessel occlusion secondary to chronic hypertension and diabetes, distal embolism, or hemodynamic compromise in the setting of carotid atherosclerosis. The absence of significant carotid stenosis in this patient, coupled with cortical distribution of infarcts, suggests that small-vessel ischemia or microembolic phenomena may have been the primary mechanism. This aligns with prior literature indicating that isolated hand weakness without sensory involvement is most frequently associated with small cortical lesions in the precentral gyrus rather than more extensive subcortical infarctions.[2]

Early neuroimaging is crucial for distinguishing central from peripheral causes of isolated upper-extremity weakness. MRI is the gold standard, detecting small cortical infarcts often missed on CT. Combining imaging with electrophysiologic studies like nerve conduction and electromyography improves accuracy by ruling out peripheral neuropathies.[2,5] Prompt diagnosis allows for secondary stroke prevention—antiplatelet therapy, risk factor control, and rehab for fine motor recovery. Hand-knob stroke often results in good functional recovery, especially when early neuroplasticity-based interventions are used. This highlights the need to consider central causes in patients with isolated distal upper-limb weakness, especially with vascular risk factors. Delay in diagnosing cortical etiology, due to suspicion of peripheral causes, can hinder management. Absence of sensory deficits or central signs doesn't exclude cortical pathology. Misdiagnosis may lead to unnecessary tests, delayed treatment, and worse outcomes. Reporting such cases emphasizes the importance of thorough neurologic assessment and prompt neuroimaging in atypical stroke presentations.

CONCLUSION

Isolated distal upper-extremity weakness can arise from small cortical infarcts in the precentral gyrus, representing the cortical hand-knob stroke. Accurate localization, early MRI, and correlation with electrophysiologic studies are essential for establishing the correct diagnosis. Management involves secondary stroke prevention, risk factor optimization, and rehabilitation to improve functional recovery. Awareness of this rare but important entity ensures timely intervention, prevents misdiagnosis, and improves patient outcomes.

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Адрес за кореспонденция
Kathleen Ann B. Pañares, MD
Department of Neurology
Chong Hua Hospital Cebu, Philippines
kathleenannbuot@gmail.com

CERVICAL MEDULLOBLASTOMA MIMICKING A NERVE SHEATH TUMOUR IN A CHILD: A RARE EXTRACRANIAL PRESENTATION

Jaimin Modh, Arvind Verma, Renish Padshala, Nazar Imam

Department of neurosurgery IKDR, Ahmedabad, India

INTRODUCTION

Medulloblastoma is the most common malignant pediatric brain tumor, accounting for nearly 20% of all childhood intracranial neoplasms. It is classified as an embryonal tumor and most commonly arises in the cerebellar vermis or hemispheres of children.¹ The 2021 World Health Organization (WHO) classification recognizes medulloblastoma as a molecularly heterogeneous entity with distinct clinical and prognostic implications.^{1,3}

Primary extracranial or spinal medulloblastomas are exceedingly rare, with only isolated case reports and small series described in the literature.^{4,6} Cervical spinal presentation without intracranial disease is particularly uncommon and often leads to diagnostic confusion.⁷

Keywords

Medulloblastoma; Schwannoma; Cervical spine

Case Report

An 8-year-old male child presented with a progressively enlarging swelling over the posterior aspect of the neck for several months. The swelling was associated with difficulty in walking and gradually progressive weakness involving all four limbs. (**Figure 1**) There was no history of trauma, fever, or constitutional symptoms.

Figure 1: Preoperative clinical photograph showing a large posterior cervical swelling.

On neurological examination, the child had features of spastic quadripareisis with motor weakness in all four limbs. Sensory examination was limited due to poor cooperation. Cranial nerve examination was unremarkable. Bladder and bowel functions were preserved.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the cervical spine revealed a large, well-defined posterior cervical mass with intraspinal extension causing significant compression of the cervical spinal cord. (**Figure 2A–C**). The lesion appeared extra-medullary and was radiologically suggestive of a cervical nerve sheath tumor, likely a schwannoma.

Figure 2A–C: Preoperative MRI cervical spine showing a well-defined posterior cervical mass with intraspinal extension causing significant spinal cord compression.

The patient was planned for surgical excision. Intraoperatively, a well-encapsulated, moderately vascular tumor was identified in the posterior cervical region with extension into the spinal canal. (**Figure 3**). Gross total excision of the tumor was achieved with adequate decompression of the spinal cord.

Figure 3: Intraoperative photograph showing exposure of the cervical tumor.

The patient was extubated on table and had had an uneventful postoperative course. Postoperatively, there was significant neurological improvement with gradual recovery of motor power in all four limbs. The postoperative wound healed well (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Postoperative clinical photograph showing healed surgical scar over the posterior cervical region.

Histopathological examination surprisingly revealed features consistent with medulloblastoma, showing sheets of small round blue cells with hyperchromatic nuclei and high mitotic activity.

DISCUSSION

Medulloblastomas occurring outside the posterior fossa are rare and their pathogenesis remains poorly understood. Several hypotheses have been proposed, including malignant transformation of ectopic embryonal cell rests, aberrant migration of neuroectodermal cells, or differentiation from pluripotent mesenchymal cells.^{4,5,8}

Spinal medulloblastomas are more commonly encountered as cerebrospinal fluid drop metastases from intracranial primaries. However, primary spinal medulloblastomas without cranial involvement have been reported in children, though infrequently.^{4,8,9}

Radiologically, these tumors may mimic benign lesions such as schwannomas or neurofibromas, especially when presenting as well-defined extramedullary masses in the cervical region.^{7,10} This radiological overlap explains the initial diagnosis of a nerve sheath tumor in the present case.

Surgical decompression remains the primary modality for symptomatic relief and tissue diagnosis. Early intervention has been shown to result in significant neurological recovery, even in aggressive tumors such as medulloblastoma.^{9,12} Given the malignant nature of the disease, adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy are recommended following histopathological confirmation.^{2,12}

CONCLUSION

Medulloblastoma should be considered in the differential diagnosis of intradural extramedullary cervical spine tumors, despite its extreme rarity at this location. Imaging characteristics alone may be misleading, and only histopathology can confirm the diagnosis. This case highlights that even classic-appearing schwannomas can turn out to be malignant embryonal tumors. Early recognition and appropriate therapy are essential for a favorable outcome.

Patient Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's parents for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

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Adress for corespondence

Dr Jaimin Modh Assistant Professor Department of neurosurgery IKDR, Ahmedabad jaimin9681@gmail.com

CORPUS CALLOSAL SPACE OCCUPYING LESION: AN INSTITUTIONAL EXPERIENCE AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Tushar Soni, Kavan Joshipura, Varshesh Shah, Shreyansh Patel

NHL Medical college, SVP Hospital Ellis Bridge, Paldi Ahmedabad, Gujarat India

INTRODUCTION:

The corpus callosum is the main bridge connecting the two brain hemispheres. The fibers from the inferior frontal and lower parietal lobes cross through the genu, while those from the parietal lobe cross at the splenium. The remaining fibers cross through the body of the corpus callosum.[1] Disorders affecting the corpus callosum are diverse and can include congenital abnormalities, demyelination, infections, trauma, and tumors. Lesions in this area often cause bilateral hemispheric effects, creating a distinctive "butterfly" pattern on imaging.[2] Gliomas involving the corpus callosum (CC) represent a unique clinical subset of brain tumors due to their deep midline location, potential for bilateral spread, and significant neurocognitive consequences. These tumors, particularly high-grade gliomas (HGGs), often present with non-localizing symptoms such as personality changes, memory loss, or limb weakness. Corpus callosum invasion, especially in so-called 'butterfly gliomas,' has historically been associated with a poor prognosis and limited surgical options. Gliomas involving the corpus callosum are a heterogeneous group, ranging from low-grade oligodendrogliomas to high-grade astrocytomas. Advances in imaging and surgical techniques have shifted treatment paradigms toward safe maximal resection, improving both survival and cognitive outcomes. Histopathological and molecular classification (IDH1, ATRX, Ki-67) is crucial in guiding prognosis and adjuvant therapy. Currently, there is no universally accepted optimal treatment; the approach generally involves biopsy, followed by radiation and chemotherapy. Due to limited data, our focus in this study is to describe the clinical features, histological diagnosis, outcomes, and survival rates of lesions affecting both hemispheres.

CASE SERIES:

Case 1:

A 43-year-old female with no known comorbidities presented with a history of irritable behaviour and forgetfulness, holocranial headache 20 days prior, right side weakness 12 days prior followed by left side weakness 10 days prior, slurring of speech 10 days prior. On presentation, she was hemodynamically stable, conscious, oriented, and following verbal commands, with bilateral pupils normally reacting to light, moving all four limbs. KPS score was 80 on presentation. MRI brain with contrast (Figure 1A & 1B) suggestive of A large lobulated, bilobed Approx 5.8 x 3.8 x 3.2 cm solid lesion involving the splenium of the corpus callosum, extending to the posterior 1/3

of the corpus callosum (midline/paramedian). It shows Hypo- to isointense on T1WI, Hyperintense on T2WI, Mild peripheral diffusion restriction on DWI, Multiple foci of blooming on SWI, on post contrast Irregular peripheral enhancement seen. The patient underwent left parieto temporo occipital craniotomy for excision of the lesion. Subtotal resection achieved. Post op CT Brain plain was done (Figure 1D). Histopathological examination (Figure 1C) demonstrated Tumor cells are moderately pleomorphic with central nuclei surrounded by clear cytoplasm. Chicken - wire type vasculature. Focal calcification and astrocytic differentiation. Micro calcification with fibrillary background. Brisk mitotic activity and microvascular proliferation is seen. Immunohistochemistry shows IDHR132H : Positive ATRX : Retained nuclear expression, p53: Occasional scattered positive cells, Ki 67: 35%, suggestive of Anaplastic oligodendroglioma, IDH 1 r132h mutant, CNS who grade 3. The patient was advised for adjuvant chemo and radiotherapy.

Figure 1: (A) Axial and (B) sagittal T1-weighted post-contrast MRI showing a large bilobed lesion involving the splenium of the corpus callosum with irregular peripheral enhancement and "butterfly" pattern (Case 1). (C) Histopathology (H&E, 400 \times) showing oligodendroglial cells with perinuclear halos and chicken-wire vasculature. (D) Postoperative non-contrast CT brain showing subtotal excision.